

NECESSARY FORMATION OF COMPLEX COMPETENCE SAFETY OF TOURIST SERVICES DURING THE DEVELOPMENT OF A STRUCTURAL-FUNCTIONAL MODEL

Abdullaev Rustamjon Abduvalievich

Kokand state pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7685630>

Abstract. *The article provides information about updating the model of competence formation in educational institutions, in physical education classes by expanding the tools of tourism activities, as well as a significant increase in recreational and tourist activities, excursion activities, animations.*

Keywords: *competence, training, physical education, tourist activity, excursion activity, animation.*

Pedagogical model means a mental image that replaces and reflects the structure and functions of a specific typologically repeated method of implementing the educational process. Modeling issues in pedagogical research Yu. It is covered in the works of A. Konarzhevsky (1996). In the conceptual construction of the pedagogical model, we studied the psychological and pedagogical works of M. M. Bakhtin (2010), V. P. Bepalko (1996), M. S. Kagan (1996), L. S. Vygotsky (2004), S. L. Rubinstein (1991). V. M. Monakhov (2000) pedagogical system, educational management system, methodological support system; considers the educational process project to be the result of pedagogical design.

The need to develop a structural and functional model, the need to form complex competences of the safety of tourist activities, today to ensure interdisciplinary relations, the components and content of training, control in the development of touristic competences, recreational orientation, security competences, first aid and due to the fact that the survival system in the natural environment is not perfect. Today, only the following "safety of life activities", "hygienic foundations of physical education and sports activities", "theory and methodology of teaching sports and wellness tourism", "physical education in children's wellness camps", "physical education and sports such subjects as "organization of events", "fitness" are mandatory. The structural and functional model we have developed includes:

-tourism project activities, case method, individual education, tourist skills, shelter installation methods, water safety rules, rock climbing gym, bike tour, lesson, meeting. general cultural competences in the form of self-improvement and self-education.;

-general professional competencies of forming personal qualities (tolerance, responsibility, discipline, diligence, communication, organizational skills, behavior in conflicts); ensuring compliance with safety requirements during professional activity, injury prevention, ability to provide first aid (practical skills in the form of business games, algorithm of actions, problem-based teaching method, work in small groups, discussion);

Professional competences in tourist activities in different types of organizations (the main form of lessons - practical and seminar classes, use of GPS-navigation maps, "rope courses" for schoolchildren, students; development of extreme trips, weekend walks project, installation of a barrier corridor with an algorithm of safety rules).

The model is based on the following principles: 1) interdisciplinary ("life safety", "hygienic foundations of physical education and sports activities", "acmeology of physical education and sports", "theory and methodology of physical education and sports", "pedagogy", "physical education and sports pedagogy" and others); 2) natural compatibility expressed in anthropogenic and man-made factors, ecological knowledge, skills of proper camp organization, human attitude to nature, plant and animal preservation skills; 3) the principle of demonstration in the form of visualizing natural conditions, navigation maps, practical determination of tourist distances, parking, walking, solving pedagogical safety problems with visual demonstration of the route; 4) the principle of competence-based content of the educational process, which distinguishes competencies, formation criteria and levels for each subject and module from the 1st to the 4th year, for this we have developed 10 criteria for the formation of competencies that meet the requirements of the subjects; 5) the principle of professional expediency in choosing tools for tourist preparation, taking into account anthropogenic factors, teaching methods, pedagogical methods to improve interactions in a group in isolation, as well as interactive excursions, situational tasks.

A competency-based approach predicted the expected outcome of vocational training in tourism; defined the necessary criteria for "knowing", "knowing", "having"; identified traditional and innovative technologies of competence formation, taking into account simulated game and non-simulated game technologies, design activities, author's technologies of survival in the natural environment, etc.

The research made it possible to identify the subjects that form the competences of tourism activity safety and the subjects that are closely related to them. The purpose of mastering the educational discipline "Safety of life activities" is to form a safe type of person who knows the basics of protecting a person, society, state, and the world community from a complex of modern dangerous factors and who can apply this knowledge in practice, representing the trends of world dynamics; citizenship, patriotism, responsibility towards oneself, society and nature. The tasks of science are to get acquainted with the dangers that threaten a person in modern life, in dangerous and emergency situations of a natural, man-made and social nature; formation of knowledge about the methods and methods of protection that allow to minimize the damage that can be caused to the person and society in dangerous emergency situations in the conditions of civil protection; includes the formation of the foundations of knowledge about the complex of modern security problems.

In our research, we tried to bring this knowledge and skills closer to the narrow-profile professional activities of physical education teachers, to practical activities in the water environment, in the forest zone, in the conditions of the rock climbing wall, and to the physical education class.

The level of formation of tourism activity safety competencies is personal qualities in preparing tourist activities for different categories of the population, acting in non-standard situations, ensuring safety in the natural environment, organizing recreation and sports tourism activities in various types of organizations, taking into account various risk-geofactors knowledge, skills and abilities such as the ability to survive in the natural environment without

Conclusion: The future physical education teacher should know the professional terminology and basic equipment, theory and methodology of sports and wellness tourism; the methodology of conducting a physical education class with elements of sports and wellness

tourism; the basics of creating a tourist route; safety rules for working on a rock climbing wall, on the water, on a bicycle and on foot, on weekends; he should also know the environmental factors and the basics of the tourist barrier corridor.

REFERENCES

1. Tolipova, O. I. "DEVELOPING STUDENT CREATIVITY AS A PSYCHOLOGICAL-PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.06 (2022): 58-61.
2. Botirova, M., S. Mirxayitova, and O. Tolipova. "PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE KERATIVENESS OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION ORGANIZATIONS."
3. Ikromovna, Tolipova Ozoda. "Formation of creativity characteristics in students of higher education organization based on CTEAM educational technology design method." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.11 (2022): 348-351.
4. OI, Tolipova. "APPROACHES TO THE STUDY AND UNDERSTANDING OF CREATIVITY TODAY." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 1319-1321.
5. Ravshanbek, Jumaboyev. "CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM, ITS BASIC PRINCIPLES AND FEATURES." *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali* 1.4 (2022): 304-309.
6. Ravshanbek, Jumaboyev. "CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM, ITS BASIC PRINCIPLES AND FEATURES." *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali* 1.4 (2022): 304-309.
7. Najmiddinovna, Rakhimova Feruza, Yuldasheva Malohat Erkinovna, and Karimova Mukarram Khalimovna. "Pedagogical Aspects Of Improving The Socio-Pedagogical Activity Of Students In Multimedia Presentations." *Journal of Positive School Psychology* 6.11 (2022): 1584-1590.
8. Nargiza, Yunusalieva. "SOCIAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS AND DEVELOPMENT OF VALUES." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.1 (2022): 300-305.
9. Najmiddinovna, Rakhimova Feruza, Yuldasheva Malohat Erkinovna, and Karimova Mukarram Khalimovna. "Pedagogical Aspects Of Improving The Socio-Pedagogical Activity Of Students In Multimedia Presentations." *Journal of Positive School Psychology* 6.11 (2022): 1584-1590.
10. Nargiza, Yunusalieva. "SOCIAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS AND DEVELOPMENT OF VALUES." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.1 (2022): 300-305.
11. Abduhafizovna, Melikuziyeva Mavluda, and Yigitaliev Mirzoxid. "Ways to increase the legal knowledge of primary school students." *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal* 3.02 (2022): 124-130.
12. Najmiddinovna, Rakhimova Feruza, Yuldasheva Malohat Erkinovna, and Karimova Mukarram Khalimovna. "Pedagogical Aspects Of Improving The Socio-Pedagogical Activity Of Students In Multimedia Presentations." *Journal of Positive School Psychology* 6.11 (2022): 1584-1590.

13. Isroilov, SH. SH. "ROLʻ KOMANDY V FORMIROVANII LICHNOSTI IGROKA." *Ekonomika i sotsium* 3-1 (2021): 583-587.
14. Najmiddinovna, Rahimova Feruza. "" GENERAL PEDAGOGY" SCIENCE PRIORITY DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 1365-1369.
15. Erkinovna, Yuldasheva Malohat. "USING THE FINNISH EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF FUTURE TEACHERS BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 1415-1420.
16. Erkinovna, Yuldasheva Malohat. "The process of development of professional and cognitive activity of students." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429* 11.09 (2022): 267-268.
17. Erkinovna, Yuldasheva Malohat. "THE ROLE OF ACTIVE LEARNING METHODS IN INCREASING THE LEARNING ACTIVITY OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL CONDITIONS." *Conferencea* (2022): 49-52.
18. Erkinovna, Yuldasheva Malohat. "THE IMPORTANCE OF INCENTIVENESS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENT ACTIVITIES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429* 11.07 (2022): 68-71.